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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a Hybrid Particle Swarm Optimization (HPSO) method that integrates the best features of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and the Evolutionary Programming (EP) techniques. The proposed HPSO method is applied to solve the Optimal Load Dispatch (OLD) problems taking in to consideration of prohibited operating zones, ramp rate limits, capacity limits and power balance constraints. In the proposed method, the best features of both PSO and EP are exploited and capable of finding optimal solutions for the non-linear optimization problems. Numerical results show that the proposed method is well suitable for solving OLD problems and it outperforms the other methods like GA, EP and PSO in terms of convergence characteristics and quality of solution.

KEYWORDS: Gaussian Mutation, Hybrid PSO, Optimal Load Dispatch, Particle Swarm optimization, Prohibited Operating Zones, Ramp-rate limit constraints.

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of OLD is to minimize the fuel cost while satisfying the load demand. Many mathematical programming methods and optimization techniques have been applied to solve the OLD problem. Lambda iteration method [2], Base Point, Participation Factor method, Gradient method and Genetic Algorithm method [3, 4] have also been reported. Among these methods the Lambda iteration method has been applied in many software packages and used by power utilities for Optimal Load Dispatch, due to ease of implementation. Since the Lambda iteration method requires a continuous problem formulation, it cannot be directly applied to OLD problems with discontinuous prohibited zones.

A considerable number of papers in the literature focus on economic aspects of the OLD under assumption that unit generation output can be adjusted instantaneously. Even though this assumption is useful because it simplifies the problem, however, it does not reflect the actual operating process of the generating units. The operating ranges for online units are actually restricted by the ramp-rate limits [5].

The Dynamic Programming (DP) method has been used to solve non-convex OLD problems, the solutions are found to be 'local optimal'. Stochastic searching algorithms such as Simulate Annealing [6], Hop Field Neural network methods [7] have been used to solve the non-convex OLD problems. However, these methods require external training routines.

Though GA method has been employed successfully to solve the complex optimization problems, recent researchers have identified some deficiencies in GA performance [4]. The premature convergence of GA degrades its performance and reduces its search capability that leads to a higher probability towards obtaining only the local optimal solution [8]. The PSO technique is applied to solve various economic load dispatch problems [12-15]. The main objective of the present work is to develop an algorithm which will give an optimal fuel cost with stable convergence characteristics. The results obtained from the proposed algorithm are compared with other methods which are developed using MatLab.

1. EP with Gaussian Mutation with scaled cost [9].
2. 2. Conventional Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [8].
3. 3. Proposed PSO Embedded with EP (HPSO).

4. The effectiveness of the proposed algorithm has been demonstrated using three different systems. The performances of the proposed algorithm are tabulated for comparison with other relevant methods EP and PSO methods.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

The objective of OLD is to minimize the total generation cost of thermal units while satisfying the various constraints. Mathematically it is stated as,

Minimize, $F_T = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i(P_i)$ ----- (1)
Where

$$f_i = a_i P_i^2 + b_i P_i + C_i \text{ \$/Hr}$$

for $P_i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$

Subject to

(i) Power Balance Constraint

$$\sum_{i=1}^N P_i = P_D + P_{loss} \text{ ----- (2)}$$

(ii) Capacity Limits Constraint

$$P_{i \min} \leq P_i \leq P_{i \max} \quad \text{where } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \text{ ----- (3)}$$

(iii) Prohibited Zone(s) Constraint

$$\begin{aligned} P_{i \min} &\leq P_i \leq P_{i1}^l \\ P_{i, k-1}^u &\leq P_i \leq P_{i, k}^l \\ P_{i, ni}^u &\leq P_i \leq P_{i \max} \quad \text{where } k=2, \dots, N \end{aligned} \text{ ----- (4)}$$

where k is the number prohibited zones of unit i

(iv) Ramp Constraint

$$\begin{aligned} P_{i \min} &= \text{Max} (P_{i \min} P_i^0 - DR_i) \\ P_{i \max} &= \text{Min} (P_{i \max} P_i^0 + UR_i) \end{aligned} \text{ ----- (5)}$$

The inequality constraints due to ramp rate limits are given as follows,

(i) If generation increases

$$P_i - P_i^0 \leq UR_i$$

(ii) If generation decreases

$$P_i^0 - P_i \leq DR_i$$

(v) Network Losses

$$P_{Loss} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N P_i B_{ij} P_j + \sum_{i=1}^N B_{0i} P_i + B_{00} \text{ ----- (6)}$$

OVERVIEW OF EP AND PSO

Four decades earlier EP was proposed for evolution of finite state machines, in order to solve prediction task. Since several modifications, enhancements, and implementations have been proposed and investigated.

Mutation is often implemented by adding a random number or a vector from a certain distribution [e.g., a Gaussian distribution in case of classical EP to a parent. The degree of variation of Gaussian mutation is controlled by its standard deviation, which is also known as a ‘strategy parameter’ in evolutionary search.

PSO is population based optimization method first proposed by Kennedy and Eberhart [10], [11]. It can be used to solve a wide range of different optimization problems like evolutionary algorithms, PSO techniques are conducting search among a population of particles. In a PSO method, particle changes the position by flying around in a multidimensional search space until computational limitations are exceeded. For each particle, at the current time step, a record is kept of the position, velocity and the best position in the search so far.

The PSO technique can generate high quality solution within shorter calculation time and more stable convergence characteristics than other stochastic methods. Figure 1 shows the general flowchart of PSO method,

Fig 1: General Flowchart of PSO method

SOLUTION METHODOLOGY OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

Step: 1 Specify the lower and upper bound generation power limits of each generating units and calculate F_{\max} and F_{\min} . Initialize randomly the individuals of the population according to limits of each unit including individual dimension, search points and velocity. These initial individual must be feasible candidate solution that satisfy the practical operating constraints. Initial velocity limits of each member in individual is as $V_{Pd}^{\max} = 0.5 * P_d^{\max}$, $V_{Pd}^{\min} = -0.5 * P_d^{\min}$.

$$P_d^{MAX} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i^{max} \quad P_d^{MIN} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i^{min}$$

Step:2 To each P_i of the population, employ B-coefficients loss formula to calculate the transmission losses [P_{Loss}].

Step: 3 Calculate evaluation value of each individual P_i using,

$$f = \frac{1}{Fcost + Ppbc} \quad \text{----- (7)}$$

where,

$$Fcost = 1 + abs \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n Fi(Pi) - Fmin \right)}{(Fmax - Fmin)} \quad \text{----- (8)}$$

$$Ppbc = 1 + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n P_i - P_D - P_{Loss} \right)^2 \quad \text{----- (9)}$$

In order to limit the evaluation value of the each individual of the population within a feasible range, before estimating the evaluation value of an individual, the generation power output must satisfy the constraints mentioned in Chapter 2.

Step: 4. Compare each individual's evaluation value with its pbest. The best evaluation value among the pbests is denoted as gbest.

Step: 5. Modify the member velocity V of the each individual P_{gi} using

$$V_{id}^{t+1} = w * V_i^{(t)} + c_1 * rand() * (pbest_{id} - p_{id}) + c_2 * Rand() * (gbest_d - p_{id}) \quad \text{----- (10)}$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad d = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Where 'n' is the population size; 'm' is the number of units and the 'w' value is set using

$$W = W_{max} - \frac{W_{max} - W_{min}}{iter_{max}} * iter \quad \text{----- (11)}$$

Where $W_{max} = 0.9$; $W_{min} = 0.4$

Step: 6.

$$\text{If } V_{id}^{(t)} > V_d^{max}, \text{ then } V_{id}^{(t+1)} = V_d^{max}$$

$$\text{If } V_{id}^{(t+1)} < V_d^{min}, \text{ then } V_{id}^{(t+1)} = V_d^{min}$$

Step: 7. Modify member position of each individual P_i using

$$P_{id}^{(t+1)} = P_{id}^{(t)} + V_{id}^{(t+1)} \quad \text{----- (12)}$$

$P_{id}^{(t+1)}$ must satisfy the constraints namely the Prohibited Zones and Ramp Rate limits described in equation (4) and (5).

Step: 8. If the evaluation value of each individual is better than the previous pbest, then current value is set to be pbest. If the best pbest is better than gbest, then the pbest is taken as gbest.

Step: 9. $P_{id}^{(t+1)'}$ created from each individual by adding to each component P_{id} , a Gaussian random variable with zero mean and standard deviation is proportional to scaled cost values.

$$P_{id}^{(t+1)'} = P_{id} + N(0, \sigma_i^2) \quad \text{----- (13)} \quad \sigma_i = \beta * \frac{f_i}{f_{i \min}} (P_{i \max} - P_{i \min}) \quad \text{----- (14)}$$

Where,

$f_{i \min}$ - Minimum cost among 'n' trial solutions.

β - Scaling factor is equal to 0.001.

f - Value of the objective function associated with vector P_{id} .

$P_{id}^{(t+1)'}$ must satisfy the constraints namely the Prohibited Zones and Ramp Rate limits described in equation (4) and (5).

Step 10: If the evaluation value of each individual is better than pbest value in step 8, the current value of pbest should be taken as gbest.

Step: 11: If the evaluation value of each individual is better than pbest value in step10 then the current value is set to be pbest. If the best pbest is better than gbest in step10, the value is set to be gbest.

Step: 12: If the values of pbest and gbest converge, go to step 13, else go to step 5.

Step: 13: The individual that generates the latest gbest is the optimal generation power of each unit with the minimum generation cost.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To verify the feasibility of the EP technique, Conventional PSO and Proposed HPSO methods were tested on three different power systems. In these examples, the Ramp-Rate limits, Prohibited Zones, capacity limits of generators and power balance equations are considered in the problem formulation. The proposed HPSO method is compared with GA [4], EP and conventional PSO methods. 100 trials are performed and observed the variations during the evolutionary process to reach convergence characteristics and fuel cost. The B-loss coefficient matrix of power system network was employed to calculate the transmission line losses. The software was written in MatLab

language and executed on third generation Intel Core i3 processor based personal computer with 2 GB DDR3 RAM. The proposed method is found to be better in solving the OLD problems.

Test System 1: A three-unit system [5] is considered and each three units has prohibited zones as well as Ramp-Rate limit constraints. Power loss is taken into account with the use of loss formula coefficient. The load demand is 300MW. The dimension of population is 100*3 and number of generations are 200. 100 trail runs were conducted and the best solutions are shown in Table 1 that satisfies the system constraints.

The proposed method gives minimum fuel cost than the other methods. Fig. 1 & Fig. 2 shows the convergence nature of the algorithm with the fuel cost. It is evident from Figure 1&2, the proposed method has better convergence characteristics than the PSO method.

Table 1 – Best Solution of three-unit system

Unit Power Output	GA [4]	EP	PSO	HPSO
P1 (MW)	194.26	200.59	193.09	202.18
P2 (MW)	50.00	74.72	85.15	75.25
P3 (MW)	79.62	38.30	34.14	34.40
TOTAL GEN (MW)	323.89	313.67	312.40	311.83
POWER LOSS (MW)	24.01	14.43	12.41	10.84
FUEL COST (\$/hr)	3737.16	3640.50	3632.10	3623.11
Evaluation Value	0.4217	0.4210	0.4146	0.4154
CPU Time (Sec)	2.96	2.12	1.95	2.20

Table 2 Results of three-unit system

The evaluation methods used are EP, conventional PSO and HPSO (100 trails)

METHODS	BEST TIME (Sec)	MEAN TIME (Sec)	MEAN COST (\$/hr)	MAX COST (\$/hr)	MIN COST (\$/hr)	MAX. EVALUATION VALUE
EP	2.96	4.33	3651.4	3681.8	3640.5	0.4210
PSO	1.95	2.12	3645.5	3652.7	3632.1	0.4181

HPSO	2.91	2.22	3636.4	3642.9	3623.1	0.4261
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Figure 1: Convergence nature of HPSO and PSO

Figure 2: Convergence property using HPSO and PSO

Test System 2: Six-unit system [8]. The system contains six thermal units 26 buses and 46 transmission lines. The load demand is 1263MW. The evolutionary process of proposed Hybrid PSO method and other methods, EP, conventional PSO method results are shown in Table 3 and Table 4. It is clear that the proposed Hybrid PSO method gives minimum fuel cost than other methods. Figure 3 and 4 shows that the Proposed Hybrid PSO method has better convergence characteristics among the PSO method.

Table 3 Best solution of the six-unit system

Unit Power Output	GA [7]	EP	PSO	HPSO
P1 (MW)	474.80	432.31	457.26	462.45
P2 (MW)	178.63	169.32	160.72	184.53
P3 (MW)	262.20	240.50	247.53	246.60
P4 (MW)	134.28	148.99	131.52	108.83
P5 (MW)	151.90	184.14	170.50	171.07
P6 (MW)	74.18	99.98	106.62	98.89
TOTAL GEN(MW)	1276.03	1275.10	1274.20	1271.90
POWER LOSS (MW)	13.02	12.07	11.15	8.98

FUEL COST (\$/hr)	15459	15451	15433	15404
Evaluation Value	0.3611	0.3510	0.3440	0.3397
CPU Time (Sec)	4.01	3.99	3.95	4.12

Table 4 Results of six-unit system.

The evaluation methods used are EP, PSO and HPSO. (100 trails)

METHODS	BEST TIME(Sec)	MEAN TIME (Sec)	MEAN COST (\$/hr)	MAX COST	MIN COST	MAX. Evaluation
EP	3.99	4.56	15472.60	15495	15451	0.3510
PSO	3.95	4.13	15452.10	15472	15433	0.3380
HPSO	4.12	4.42	15431.12	15449	15404	0.3450

Figure 3: Convergence nature of HPSO and PSO

Figure 4: Convergence nature of HPSO and PSO

Test System 3: 15-Unit system [8]. This system contains 15 thermal units with Prohibited Zones and Ramp Rate limit constraints. The load demand of the system is 2630MW. The losses are calculated using B-loss coefficients. The dimension of the population is 100*15 and number of generations are 200. The experiment results are shown in Table5 & Table6. The proposed Hybrid PSO method gives minimum fuel cost than the other methods and also stable convergence and avoids premature convergence, shown in figure 5 and figure 6.

Table 5 Best solution of the 15-unit system

Unit Power Output	GA [7]	EP	PSO	HPSO
P1 (MW)	415.31	455.00	455.00	455.00
P2 (MW)	359.72	380.00	380.00	380.00
P3 (MW)	104.42	116.13	130.00	130.00
P4 (MW)	74.99	119.06	130.00	130.00
P5 (MW)	380.28	157.26	150.00	170.00
P6 (MW)	426.79	460.00	460.00	460.00
P7 (MW)	341.32	430.00	430.00	430.00
P8 (MW)	124.79	151.68	60.00	61.72
P9 (MW)	133.14	52.17	74.01	62.54
P10 (MW)	89.26	99.11	160.00	160.00
P11 (MW)	60.06	52.27	80.00	80.00
P12 (MW)	50.00	65.48	80.00	80.00
P13 (MW)	38.78	49.77	26.88	25.00
P14 (MW)	41.94	35.85	21.74	15.00
P15 (MW)	22.64	34.96	15.00	15.00
TOTAL GEN (MW)	2668.40	2658.70	2652.50	2654.30
POWER LOSS (MW)	38.28	28.70	22.65	24.26
FUEL COST (\$/hr)	33113	32881	32640	32633
Evaluation Value	0.3150	0.3086	0.3132	0.3259
CPU Time (sec)	19.31	10.75	6.23	11.70

Table 6 Results of 15-unit system. The evaluation methods used are EP, PSO and HPSO (100 trails)

METHODS	BEST TIME (Sec)	MEAN TIME (Sec)	MEAN COST (\$/hr)	MAX COST (\$/hr)	MIN COST (\$/hr)	MAX. Evaluation Value
EP	10.75	10.95	32954	33078	32881	0.3086
PSO	6.23	5.46	32693	32715	32640	0.3132
HPSO	11.69	8.01	32680	32701	32633	0.3259

Figure 5: Convergence nature of HPSO and PSO

Figure 6: Convergence nature of HPSO and PSO

CONCLUSION

In this paper, Evolutionary Programming technique, conventional PSO and proposed HPSO methods are applied successfully to solve the OLD problems. The proposed HPSO method has been proved to have superior features in terms of achieving better optimal solutions for reducing the fuel cost of the generating units and better convergence characteristics. Non-linear characteristics of the generators such as ramp-rate limits, prohibited zones, non-smooth cost functions are considered for the selected test systems. The numerical results confirm that the effectiveness of the proposed method over the other methods.

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